

GLAM Labs

Annual Report 2024

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GLAM Labs are:

Instrumental for **effecting the digital shift in cultural heritage institutions** by challenging traditional approaches.

Bringing institutions, technology, people and communities together through **experimental ways of working**.

Based in **a variety of cultural heritage institutions** including national and state-based libraries, university galleries, libraries, archives and museums.

Operating at the **intersection** of digital cultural heritage, innovation, technology and creativity, Labs benefit organisations, users, society and culture.

GLAMLABS.IO/MEMBER-MAP/

Do you want to appear in the map? Please, send us the Wikidata link of your institution.

Contact email

Email for contact

Wikidata link of your institution

E.g.: <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q4935493>.

Check if your institution is on Wikidata!

Try to find your institution at Wikidata and retrieve the element which corresponds to your institution.

Wikidata Query Service

Leaflet | Wikimedia | © OpenStreetMap contributors

As of 31/12/2024

- **88 institutions** <https://w.wiki/BrEZ> ➡ please send us Wikidata ID of your institution if you would like to add your Lab to this list

There are **360 members** on the <https://www.jiscmail.ac.uk/GLAMLABS> (accessed 31/12/2024), ➡ please spread the word!

Core Group

- Organise meetings and webinars
- Coordination
- Propose dates and location for in person meetings
- Website
- Zenodo community and Zotero bibliography

Team:

- **Katrine Gasser** - Royal Danish Library
- **Nele Gabriëls** - KU Leuven
- **Olga Holownia** - International Internet Preservation Consortium
- **Mahendra Mahey** - Tallinn University
- **Sally Chambers** - British Library - DARIAH-EU
- **Gustavo Candela** - University of Alicante

Action Group

- Regular meetings to exchange ideas and knowledge through webinars, presentations at events, articles
- Contributions to the Annual Report

Sarah Ames, National Library of Scotland

Filipe Bento, Universidade de Aveiro

Julie Birkholz, Universiteit Gent

Paula Bray, State Library of Victoria

Gustavo Candela, Universidad de Alicante

Sally Chambers, Universiteit Gent, British Library, DARIAH

Steven Claeysens, Koninklijke Bibliotheek

Caleb Derven, University of Limerick

Milena Dobрева, University of Strathclyde

Joseph Dunnigan, Banned Books Museum

Nele Gabriëls, KU Leuven

Katrine Gasser, Det Kgl. Bibliotek

Philippe Genêt, Die Deutsche Nationalbibliothek

Olga Holownia, International Internet Preservation Consortium

Alba Irollo, Europeana

Victor Harbo Johnston, Det Kgl. Bibliotek

Johannes Knüchel, Österreichische Nationalbibliothek

Kristy Kokegei, History Trust of South Australia

Benjamin Lee, University of Washington

Peter Leinen, Die Deutsche Nationalbibliothek

Emily Maemura, University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign

Mahendra Mahey, University of Strathclyde, Tallinn University, Estonian National Museum

Simon Mayer, Österreichische Nationalbibliothek

Stephanie Nitsche, Die Deutsche Nationalbibliothek

Rania Osman, Bibliotheca Alexandrina

Abigail Potter, Library of Congress

Emma Rende, Kungliga biblioteket – Sveriges nationalbibliotek

Armin Straube, University of Limerick

Ellen Van Keer, Meemoo

Lotte Wilms, Fontys University

Events

2024

- Core Group meetings

MAY 2024 DHNB Conference in Reykjavík

- In person meeting at the National and University Library of Iceland
- GLAM Labs panel
- Workshop “GLAM Labs: a Jupyter Notebook approach” [\[article\]](#)

SEPTEMBER 2024 TPDL Conference in Ljubljana

- In person meeting at the National and University Library of Slovenia
- GLAM Labs poster “Using Wikidata in GLAM” [\[poster\]](#)

NOVEMBER 2024: WEBINAR

- “Publication and reuse of digital collections: A GLAM Labs approach” [\[slides\]](#)

NOVEMBER 2024: RDA Plenary

- “Gathering Metrics and Setting Boundaries: Reusing Collections as Data and the impacts of AI” [\[more information\]](#)

DECEMBER 2024: ACTION GROUP MEETING

“PUBLICATION AND REUSE OF DIGITAL COLLECTIONS: A GLAM LABS APPROACH” PANEL AT DHNB 2024 CONFERENCE, REYKJAVÍK, 29 MAY 2024. PHOTO CREDIT: OLGA HOLOWNIA.

TPDL 2024
The 28th International
Conference on Theory and
Practice of Digital Libraries

Events – November webinar

- **Olga Holownia & Mahendra Mahey**
Introduction to GLAM Labs as a community, recent projects and next steps
- **Nele Gabriëls & Gustavo Candela**
Introduction to Checklist for Publishing Collections as Data
- **Katrine Hofmann**
Connecting people with data at KB Labs at the Royal Library of the Netherlands: lessons learned from collaborative projects and initiatives
- **Gustavo**
Reusing digital collections from a Jupyter Notebook approach (DHNB 2024 workshop)

Events: TPDL - Using Wikidata in GLAM

Candela, G., Cuper, M., Holownia, O., Gabriëls, N., Dobрева, M., Mahey, M. (2024). A Systematic Review of Wikidata in GLAM Institutions: a Labs Approach. In: Antonacopoulos, A., *et al.* Linking Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries. TPDL 2024. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 15178. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-72440-4_4

<https://github.com/hibernator11/wikidata-review>

The 28th International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries

TPDL 2024

WIKIDATA

International
GLAM Labs
Community

TPDL 2024

A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF WIKIDATA IN GLAM INSTITUTIONS: A LABS APPROACH

GALLERIES, LIBRARIES, ARCHIVES AND MUSEUMS LABS | GLAMLABS.IO

Objectives

- To provide a systematic review of Wikidata use in GLAM institutions
- To assess the benefits and limitations of using Wikidata in GLAM projects

Examples of GLAM Labs initiatives related to Wikidata

- Data Foundry at the National Library of Scotland | data.nls.uk
- Rijksmuseum in the Netherlands | data.rijksmuseum.nl
- LOD Infrastructure for Digital Humanities in Finland | seco.cs.aalto.fi/projects/loidi4h
- National Library of Spain | datos.bne.es
- Wikidata projects of National Library of the Netherlands | www.koninklijkebibliothek.nl/over-de-glam-wikidata-activiteiten

Research questions and findings

	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4
1 How is Wikidata described in the current GLAM literature?	properties schema large ontology semantic model ontological model	free and structured database structured data source central data management platform freely available hosted platform	collaborative knowledge base knowledge base knowledge graph Web-based knowledge graph	tool for new working methods collaborative and global metadata source environment for data storage, curation & extraction tool of bibliographic interest in the Semantic Web
2 What types of experimentation with Wikidata are emerging in the GLAM domain?	Each of the topics have been categorised using the TaDIRAM taxonomy https://ta.diram.artor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data curation and publication Data extraction and visualisation Data enrichment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data analysis Data mapping Data quality 	
3 What are the challenges associated with Wikidata in GLAM?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Imbalanced data coverage and quality in Wikidata Editing exercise is limited due to the lack of reliable citations Lack of information in Wikidata may affect reconciliation services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Historical injustices and imbalances in information representation Quality of use requires improvement regarding authority control and the adoption of advanced metadata vocabularies, including provenance information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Since Wikidata is not originally designed as a bibliographic tool: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> quality and completeness of bibliographic data are usually high, but not certain and current ontology models for cataloguing rely on metadata structures involving three or more tiers that are not in Wikidata 	

Conclusions

- Summary of 38 research articles on Wikidata projects published 2020-2023 (Source: Web of Science and Scopus online research databases)
- Publicly available dataset available in a GitHub repository
- Datasets extracted from Wikidata and a README file describing the project and extraction process
- Results show Wikidata has been used for different purposes in GLAMs
- Wikidata reuse, an important FAIR principle, can be better integrated into the practices of GLAMs

Next steps

- Expanding the search strategy and integrating additional projects and approaches which can be found on Wikimedia pages
- Incorporating projects provided by other repositories and conferences
- Increasing the number of articles by adjusting the time period

Bubble chart obtained from the SPARQL endpoint of Wikidata describing the main subjects covered by the projects. The size of the bubbles indicates the relevancy of the keywords in the selection of works.

github.com/hibernator11/wikidata-review

Gustavo Candela*, Mirjam Cuper¹, Olga Holownia², Niels Gabriëls³, Milana Dobрева⁴, and Maheyra Maney⁵
¹University of Alicante, ²KB, National Library of the Netherlands, ³International Internet Preservation Consortium, ⁴KU Leuven Libraries, ⁵University of Strathclyde, ⁶Taipei University

✉ Gustavo Candela | g.candela@gu.es

Initiatives – Research Data Alliance

Collections as Data Interest Group

Gathering Metrics and Setting Boundaries: Reusing Collections as Data and the impacts of AI

1. Welcome and Introduction to the new IG (10-15 min)
2. Presentations (30-40 min)
 - a. Gustavo Candela, International GLAM Labs
 - b. Santi Thompson & Ayla Stein Kenfield, D-CRAFT
 - c. Mahendra Mahey, Evolving GLAM Labs
3. Break-out discussions on policy decisions supporting reuse (40-45 min)

What lessons can be learned from the establishment, impact and evolution of GLAM Labs?

How institutions are tracking and encouraging reuse of collections as data? What kinds of metrics do we want to track?

With many thanks
to Beth Knazook

Collaborative notes: https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/collections-as-data-ig/plenary-participation/?application_id=171818

Session recording: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-QxUDg50Nqs>

Initiatives – DHwiki Dariah Working Group

DHwiki

This Working Group is a space for discussion and dissemination of use case experiences and best practices around Wikibase and Wikidata in a DH context, and for contributions to further developing the Wikibase software and related tools.

With many thanks to
David Lindemann

<https://www.dariah.eu/activities/working-groups/dhwiki/>

Initiatives – European data space for cultural heritage

Collections as Data

The common European data space is a European Union flagship to accelerate the digital transformation of the cultural heritage sector.

As partners in the data space consortium, the Europeana Foundation and DARIAH work together to connect this sector with academia and research, as well as reinforcing the collaboration with relevant networks and communities including the GLAM Labs Community.

Inspired by the Collections as Data movement, they also lead on the 'Collections as Data' strand of work, developing tools, creating training materials, organising workshops and giving presentations focussing on the curation and publication of datasets suitable for computational use, especially in data-driven research.

<https://pro.europeana.eu/page/common-european-data-space-for-cultural-heritage>

Initiatives – Datasheets for Digital Cultural Heritage

Datasheets

This Working Group, set up within the Europeana Research Community and EuropeanaTech Community, works to adapt the concept of datasheets for the cultural heritage sector.

<https://doi.org/10.5334/johd.124>

<https://pro.europeana.eu/project/datasheets-for-digital-cultural-heritage-working-group>

Initiatives – Datasheets for Web Archives Toolkit

Datasheets

Collaboration between Emily Maemura (University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign) & Helena Byrne (British Library).

This toolkit provides information on the creation of datasheets for web archives datasets.

Composed of several parts including templates, examples, and guidance documents.

Toolkit: <https://doi.org/10.22020/rq8z-r112>

Framework implemented with new UKWA Data Sets:
<https://bl.iro.bl.uk/collections/5379d014-1774-46e1-a96a-7089e7c814a3?locale=en>

Initiatives – Towards a National Collection

Unlocking the Potential of Digital Collections. A call to action

This document presents the policy recommendations of **Towards a National Collection** (TaNC), a five-year, £18.9 million investment in the UK's world-renowned museums, archives, libraries and galleries, with funding provided through UK Research and Innovation's Strategic Priorities Fund and delivered by the Arts and Humanities Research Council (AHRC).

The recommendations detail an end-to-end process, with case-study examples and supported by detailed training materials, which we ask UK cultural heritage institutions and their funders to adopt to help build a unified UK digital collection.

Case study 2:

Collections as Data – GLAM data labs

The perspective of Collections as Data focuses on making digital collections from galleries, libraries, archives and museums (GLAM) accessible for computational use. This involves providing clear licensing, detailed metadata and documentation, structured datasets, and utilising public platforms and APIs to facilitate these collections' reuse, analysis and exploration.

This initiative is championed by the International GLAM Labs Community, which has been empowering the GLAM sector to adapt to digital transformation by promoting tools like Jupyter Notebooks and data accessibility to enhance the utility of cultural heritage in the digital realm. Their work is important in modernising collections management, encouraging innovative research and expanding public engagement with heritage resources.

Bailey, R., Pereda, J., Michaels, C., & Callahan, T. (2024). Unlocking the Potential of Digital Collections. A call to action. Towards a National Collection. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13838916>

Publications

- Claeysens, S. (2024). Publishing Large Collections of Digitised Printed Material - The National Library of the Netherlands. *The Routledge Companion to Libraries, Archives, and the Digital Humanities*, Chapter 14, p. 204-215. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003327738-17>
- Candela, G., Holownia, O., Odsbjerg, M., Cuper, M., Gabriëls, N., Hofmann, K., Gray, E.J., Chambers, S. and Mahey, M. (2025). Promoting Computational Access to Digital Collections in the Nordic and Baltic Countries: An Icelandic Use Case. *Journal of Open Humanities Data*, 11(1), p. 7. <https://doi.org/10.5334/johd.261>
- Magnus, B., Priem, M., Vanderperren, N., Berghe, P., Keer, E., Vissers, R. (2025). "Metadata creation and enrichment using artificial intelligence at meemoo," *Journal of Digital Media Management*, Henry Stewart Publications, vol. 13 (2), p. 110-123, January.
- Candela, G. (2024). Browsing Linked Open Data in Cultural Heritage: a shareable visual configuration approach. *J. Comput. Cult. Herit.* <https://doi.org/10.1145/3707647>
- Candela, G., Cuper, M., Holownia, O., Gabriëls, N., Dobрева, M., Mahey, M. (2024). A Systematic Review of Wikidata in GLAM Institutions: a Labs Approach. In: Antonacopoulos, A., et al. *Linking Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries. TPD L 2024. Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, vol 15178. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-72440-4_4

Publications

- Knazook, E. (2024). Nineteenth-Century Canadian Photographically Illustrated Books Online: Examining and Sharing a Research Collection as Data. Electronic Thesis and Dissertation Repository. <https://ir.lib.uwo.ca/etd/10633>
- Candela, G., Gabriëls, N., Chambers, S., Dobрева, M., Ames, S., Ferriter, M., Fitzgerald, N., Harbo, V., Hofmann, K., Holownia, O., Irollo, A., Mahey, M., Manchester, E., Pham, T.-A., Potter, A. and Van Keer, E. (2023). A checklist to publish collections as data in GLAM institutions. Global Knowledge, Memory and Communication, Vol. ahead-of-print No. ahead-of-print. <https://doi.org/10.1108/GKMC-06-2023-0195>
- Candela, G., Chambers, S., & Sherratt, T. (2023). An approach to assess the quality of Jupyter projects published by GLAM institutions. Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology, p. 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.24835>
- Dobрева, M., Stefanov, K. & Ivanova, K. Data Spaces for Cultural Heritage: Insights from GLAM Innovation Labs. 7 Dec 2022, From Born-Physical to Born-Virtual: Augmenting Intelligence in Digital Libraries. Tseng, Y-H., Katsurai, M. & Nguyen, H. N. (eds.). p. 492-500 9 p. (Lecture Notes in Computer Science; vol. 13636).

Journal of Open Humanities Data

Promoting Computational Access to Digital Collections in the Nordic and Baltic Countries: An Icelandic Use Case

Gustavo Candela, Olga Holownia, Max Odsbjerg, Mirjam Cuper, Nele Gabriëls, Katrine Hofmann, Edward J. Gray, Sally Chambers, Mahendra Mahey

Extension of the workshop delivered at the 2024 edition of DHNB Conference.

<https://doi.org/10.5334/johd.261>

Presentations & workshops

- Milena Dobрева, Gustavo Candela. Computational access to digital collections - University of Strathclyde. 5 February 2024. [[more information](#)]
- Alba Irollo, Sally Chambers, Gustavo Candela. A workflow to publish Collections as Data - training workshop. 13 February 2024. [[more information](#)]
- Gustavo Candela, Nele Gabriëls, and Vicky Dritsou. A Collections as Data Workflow: from user needs to training opportunities. Collections as Data: Collaborating across Data Spaces for Cultural Heritage and Open Science. 19-20 February 2024.
- Gustavo Candela, Mirjam Cuper, Olga Holownia, and Max Pedersen. Reusing digital collections from GLAM Labs: a Jupyter Notebook approach, DHNB Conference in Reykjavik. 29 May 2024. [[article](#)]
- Gustavo Candela. Workflows para la publicación de colecciones como datos. I Workshop CLARIAH-CM, Complutense University of Madrid. 30-31 May 2024. [[slides](#)]
- Gustavo Candela. Workshop Computational access to digital collections in GLAM institutions: a reproducible approach. Laboratório de Humanidades Digitais. 5 September 2024. [[more information](#)]

Presentations & workshops

- Sally Chambers, Gustavo Candela, and Tomasz Parkola. From Theory to Practice: Integrating State-of-the-art Digitization Research Into Day-to-day Digitization Practices and Operations. TPDL Conference in Slovenia. 24 September 2024. [[more information](#)]
- Meltem Dişli, Gustavo Candela. Assessing data quality of Linked Open Data in Cultural Heritage institutions. LD4 Conference. 11 October 2024. [[more information](#)]
- Sally Chambers. Exploring Collections as Data in the European context: current initiatives, future prospects. Open and Engaged 2024: Empowering Communities to Thrive in Open Scholarship. British Library. 21 October 2024. [[slides](#)]
- Gustavo Candela. Developing Workflows to Publish Collections as Data. Open and Engaged 2024: Empowering Communities to Thrive in Open Scholarship. British Library. 21 October 2024. [[slides](#)]
- Gustavo Candela. Using Wikidata in the GLAM context: A Collections as data approach. Wikidata days, Lisbon. 15 November 2024. [[slides](#)]
- Sally Chambers. Towards sustainable workflows for newspapers as datasets: an infrastructural perspective. ONB Labs Symposium 2024. 25-26 November 2024
- Gustavo Candela. Reutilización de colecciones GLAM como datos. II Jornada de Patrimonio Bibliográfico de la Comunidad de Madrid. 27 November 2024. [[more information](#)]

Presentations & workshops

User needs regarding implementing Collections as Data at GLAM institutions

Nele Gabriëls, KU Leuven Libraries

Collections as Data: Collaborating across
Data Spaces for Cultural Heritage and Open Science
KBR | Royal Library of Belgium, 19th - 20th February 2024

Fellowships

- **Gustavo Candela - Reusing Bibliographic content - [Blog post](#)**
[Atrium Transnational Access Scheme Grants](#) in collaboration with the Polish Literary Bibliography/European Literary Bibliography (IBL-PAN), the Institute of Literary Research of the Polish Academy of Sciences and the Digital Research Infrastructure for the Humanities (eHum PSNC).

Transnational Access – Travel Grants

ATRIUM will offer researchers and research teams the chance to visit 16 research infrastructures and organisations in the Arts and Humanities abroad.

[More info](#)

<https://atrium-research.eu/travel-grants/>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14106707>

PhD Research in GLAM Labs

- **Mahendra Mahey** started at PhD at the University of Strathclyde from 2024-2027
- Supervisors: Dr Milena Dobрева and Professor Ian Ruthven
- **Working title:**
What lessons can be learned from the life-cycle, impact, evolution and future of Gallery, Library, Archive and Museum (GLAM) Labs?

University of
Strathclyde
Glasgow

A detailed illustration of a vintage laboratory setup, rendered in a light blue, wireframe style. The scene includes a balance scale on the left, a large round-bottom flask on a stand in the center, and various other glass vessels and apparatuses on the right. The background is a light, textured blue.

Updates from Labs

ONB Labs

Austrian National Library

labs.onb.ac.at

Contact:

labs@onb.ac.at

johannes.knuechel@onb.ac.at

- [ONB Labs Symposium 2024](#)
 - Reworking of [Data Sets](#)
 - Publishing new [Data Sets](#)
 - Jesuit Chronicles
 - Johann Caspar Lavater Collection
 - Esperanto Newspaper Excerpts
 - [Glossary](#)
-

ONB Labs

- ONB Labs Symposium 2024
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 - Johann Caspar Lavater Collection
 - Esperanto Newspaper Excerpts
- Glossary

A retrospective of the ONB Labs Symposium “Newspapers as Datasets,” November 25th and 26th, 2024

LC Lab

Library of Congress
labs.loc.gov

- LC 4 Robots -> data.labs.loc.gov
 - Innovator in Residence
 - Machine Learning Experiments
 - AI Planning Framework
-

labs.loc.gov

Exploratory Data Packages

<https://data.labs.loc.gov/packages/>

Hidden Portals

<https://labs.loc.gov/work/experiments/portals/>

[Introducing the LC Labs Artificial Intelligence](#)

[Planning Framework](#) (blog post)

The screenshot displays the 'LIBRARY LABS Experiments' page. At the top, it states: 'We use emerging technologies and digital methods to enhance the impact of the Library's digital collections.' Below this, a grid of 30 experiment thumbnails is shown, each with a title and a small image or graphic. The experiments include:

- Seeing Like an Explorer
- AI at LC
- Comparing Cultural Heritage in the Cloud
- Experimental Access
- Humans in the Loop
- Speculative Annotation
- LOC 3D
- Citizen DJ
- Navigator Navigator
- Random Maps Navigator
- Exploring Machine Learning with the Project Gutenberg
- Search in Text Viewer
- Collection Wisdom
- PDF Metadata Tool
- By the People crowd.loc.gov
- Microtypography
- Web Archive Database
- 2019 There is one summary for H.R. 5515 by 26 members. See amendments and H.R. 5515, by a vote of Congress per Browser Extension
- Digital Literacy
- Political Cartoon Viewer
- Free to Use Browser Extension
- Mapping an American Facies
- Beyond Words
- Congressional Data Challenge
- Viewer for Metadata per Page
- Library of Congress Colors
- Photo Roulette
- Business News
- CONGRESS LAB
- Machine Paper Series

KB Lab

The national library of the Netherlands
lab.kb.nl

- (Enriched) datasets
 - Research output
 - Tools for working with our digitized collections
 - Tutorials
 - Blogs
-

lab.kb.nl

Highlights

- Opening of the KB Datalab in the reading rooms of the library!
- 10 years Researcher-in-Residence Program
- First edition of the KB Summer School

KB } national library
of the netherlands

Tool

NL-Menu
NL-menu was the first Dutch web index which was restored in 2018.

Canonizer
The Canonizer demonstrates how well canonicity can be classified based on the text of a novel.

Annif
Assisted keyword assignment using Annif
Annif can be used to make cataloging more efficient by suggesting authors and keywords.

Delpher
Delpher demo: pandemics through time (Dutch)
Delpher demo was produced to inspire ideas on how to showcase digital heritage collections.

Word embedding playground
Word embedding playground provides tools for training and fine-tuning word embedding models.

Brinkeys
Brinkeys Tool
Brinkeys is a demo that suggest a number of Brinman topics for a dissertation based on its contents.

Narralyzer
Narralyzer finds and visualises characters in texts and the relationships between them.

CanOT
CanOT shows the canonicity curves of publications related to 21 selected authors or texts/figures.

RDA Entity Finder
The RDA Entity Finder enables browsing through several bibliographic entities.

Narralyzer
Narralyzer finds and visualises characters in texts and the relationships between them.

Data Foundry

National Library of Scotland
data.nls.uk

- Metadata, digitised collections, spatial data and organisational data
 - Examples of use based on Jupyter Notebooks and featured projects
 - Adoption of collections as data principles
 - Open Data publication plan
 - Organisational AI statement
-

data.nls.uk

Current initiatives

- [The National Library of Scotland Fellowship in Digital Research 2024-2025](#)
- [National Library of Scotland AI Statement](#)
 - Sets out a careful approach to AI
- [Jupyter Notebooks](#)
- Collaborations with postgraduate courses
- 5 years since launch of Data Foundry: wider review of platform and underlying workflows including ATR

With many thanks to:

Edward J. Gray, Agiatis Benardou, Vicky Dritsou, Toma Tasovac, Thomas Padilla, Beth Knazook, Tomasz Umerle, Cezary Rosiński, Arek Margraf, Tomasz Parkola, Péter Király, Meltem Dişli, Matthew Connelly, Courtney Chartier, Alba Comino Comino, Rosario Arquero Avilés, Jesús Pradells, Dolores Romero, Mikel Irukieta, Javier Pereda, Antoine Isaac, Jon Carlstedt Tønnessen, Henk Alkemade, Nuno Freire, Jörg Lehmann, Giulia Osti, Selda Eren, Jez Cope, Mirjam Cuper, Rossitza Atanassova, Helena Byrne, Nora McGregor, Yasmeen Shorish, Hannah Scates Kettler, Santi A. Thompson, Gimena del Rio Riande and **all the people involved in the Action Group**.

And also to the following initiatives:

[European data space for cultural heritage](#), [History Lab - Columbia University](#), [Skills4EOSC](#), [DHWiki Working Group](#), [DARIAH-EU](#), [ATRIUM](#), [Towards a National Collection](#), [the Europeana Datasheets for digital cultural heritage Working Group](#), [LIBER](#), [the Research Data Alliance Collections as data IG](#), and [the Impact Centre of Competence in digitisation](#).